

Cult of Thecla

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The cult of Thecla was a widespread and popular devotion to Saint Thecla, reportedly a follower of Paul the Apostle. The foundational text of this report is the Acts of (Paul and) Thecla, a second century Greek story about the young virgin Thecla who renounces her betrothed in order to live a life of sexual abstinence. As the story goes, Thecla survived multiple attempts by the local authorities of public execution, making her a model of eventual martyrdom ideologies. Though some Christians thought the tale a forgery (notably Tertullian), in the third to seventh centuries devotion of Thecla spread across the Mediterranean, rivaling devotion to Mary the mother of Jesus. From Syria to Africa, Greece, and Spain, reverence to Thecla consisted of shrines, catacombs, churches and pilgrimages dedicated to her. While reverence to Thecla as a saint continues today, late antiquity was the high point of such adherence. The types of people who participated in the cult of Thecla varied dramatically. Evagrius Scholasticus of the sixth century, for instance, records in his Ecclesiastical History that the fifth century emperor Zeno had a vision of Thecla, who encouraged him to march on Byzantium to reclaim his throne, which he did. Afterwards, Zeno had a church built to Thecla in Seleucia, home of a center of Theclan cultic activity. One of the functions of shrines, however, was to provide shelter to pilgrims, who both gave offerings and received sustenance. This cultic economy necessitates involvement from both those wealthy and powerful enough to act as benefactors to the cult (such as in the construction of the shrines themselves) and those of the (majority) poor who sought out the shrines to pay homage to the saint, hoping to receive blessings in return. As described by the fourth century pilgrim Egeria, the cult complex in Seleucia had "innumerable monastic cells of men and of women," with a head deaconess overseeing the virgins housed there. Personal piety was also a major factor of the cult, which can be difficult to track for the majority of people. Items such as flasks or combs with engravings of Thecla are abundant, along with paintings and reliefs of scenes from the Acts of (Paul and) Thecla, as most notably evident in the Catacomb of Thecla (Rome) and the chapel at El Bagawat (Egypt). Famous Christians such as Gregory of Nyssa and Gregory of Nazianzus extolled Thecla as a moral exemplar, the latter even temporarily relocating to the shrine in Seleucia. This reverence reflected the concern for the body in some Christian circles, emphasizing the imperative of sexual purity, if not outright abstinence. It is implausible to imagine these kinds of moral ideologies belonged to the elite (for which have the most evidence) alone. Given Tertullian's early negative disposition against the Acts of Thecla for the baptismal authority it seemed to grant women, it is no surprise that women in particular found power in the character of Thecla who defied the men of her life (even Paul!) to live an exemplary (chaste) Christian life.

Date Range: 150 CE - 600 CE

Region: Mediterranean

Region tags: Syria, Asia Minor, Levant, Greece, Egypt, Turkey, Anatolia

Sporadically throughout the Mediterranean, particularly in the East and in Egypt.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Stephen J. Davis, *The Cult of Saint Thecla: A Tradition of Women's Piety in Late Antiquity*
- Source 1: Léonie Hayne, "Thecla and the Church Fathers," in *Vigiliae Christianae*, vol. 48 no. 3 (September 1994), 209-218
- Source 1: Scott Fitzgerald Johnson, *The Life and Miracles of Thekla: A Literary Study* (2006)
- Source 1: Shelly Matthews, "Thinking of Thecla," in *Journal of Feminist Studies in Religion*, vol. 17(2) (2001), 39-55

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: http://www.patrologia-lib.ru/apocryph/novum/a_paul.htm
- Source 1 Description: Greek text of the entire Acts of Paul, with the Acts of (Paul and) Thecla from Mendelssohn, *Acta Apostolorum Apocrypha*, vol. 1 (1891)
- Source 2 URL: <http://www.earlychristianwritings.com/text/actspaul.html>
- Source 2 Description: English translation of The Acts of Paul and Thecla from M. R. Jameson, *The Apocryphal New Testament* (1924)
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.collectionscanada.gc.ca/obj/thesescanada/vol2/002/NR81475.PDF>
- Source 3 Description: English translation of *The Life and Miracles of Thecla*

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Some tenets were seen as transgressive given the ways that women were empowered, as against more patriarchal ideologies that were pervasive in early Christianity and imperial circles.

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: While some men (such as Tertullian) were antagonistic to the story of Thecla, the cult developed a widespread adherence and many traveled to shrines, both men and women.

Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There were varieties of responses to Thecla, and it is likely that many would not have cared one way or another.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: While there was not a strict assignment of adherence by gender, it does appear that women were especially drawn to Thecla more so than men.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

Notes: While specific rituals inducting a person into the veneration of Thecla was not standard, rituals inducting people into Christianity (particularly baptism) were often previously enacted.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Notes: One may argue about the nature of proselytization (whether it can in actuality be non-coercive). While there was not an active coercive process to bring people to venerate Thecla, general pressures that brought people to any given cult practice were likely present, especially for women. If women were drawn to leadership roles in the cult of Thecla because of the same authority being denied them elsewhere in society, that could be seen as a form of coercion (the promise of benefits).

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Before either the separation of church and state or strong centralization across the Roman Empire, shrines or statues would have been set up by municipal authorities, who may have also been clergy. Emperor Zeno was famously a patron to Thecla after supposedly receiving a vision from her (according to Evagrius Scholasticus, Ecclesiastical History 3.8).

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: While apostasy was certainly a concept in wider Christianity, there would not have been an equivalent form of apostasy for the specific cult of Thecla, as people were not exclusively tied to veneration of one saint or another in an official capacity in the same way as various imperial forms of Christianity.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The nature of the cult of Thecla makes it impossible to gauge the number of adherents, aside from that it was extremely popular. Egeria (4th century) notes of Seleukeia that there were "very many monastic cells" at the church dedicated to Thecla in Seleukeia (Journey to the Holy Land, 23.4). Piety directed towards Thecla could take the form of a pilgrimage, an offering, the building of a shrine or church, all of which were common in antiquity and difficult/impossible to track precisely. For instance, when the emperor Zeno built the church to Thecla, we cannot assume that every attendee knew or cared about Thecla.

Reference: Paul Bradshaw F. Egeria, Journey to the Holy Land. Brepols. isbn: 978-2-503-59281-7.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The nature of the cult of Thecla makes it impossible to gauge the number of adherents, aside from that it was extremely popular. Piety directed towards Thecla could take the form of a pilgrimage, an offering, the building of a shrine or church, all of which were common in antiquity and difficult/impossible to track precisely. For instance, when the emperor Zeno built the church to Thecla, we cannot assume that every attendee knew or cared about Thecla.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

Notes: While many would have considered foundational text sacrosanct, the overwhelming evidence from antiquity is that texts were modified quite frequently. Aside from the many variations of the New Testament writings, in the 2nd and 3rd centuries (before there was a "New Testament") many texts contended for revered status, and the Acts of Thecla were among them. Even still, the Acts of Thecla appears to have two endings, one that was tagged on either in addition or to replace the original ending. Furthermore, the base narrative itself seems to have originated independently before being merged with the other texts in the Acts of Paul. The text may have been viewed as unalterable, but these changes were most likely made by pious admirers of Thecla, not those (like Tertullian) who viewed the legend as false (On Baptism, 17).

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Notes: There were certainly communities who would have had their own "canons" in the early centuries of the cult, but in the 2nd-5th centuries the Christian canon varied widely (the earliest extant account of the 27 books in the current mainstream Christian New Testament is Athanasius's festal letter [39] of 367 CE). Important texts such as the four now canonical gospels (Mark, Matthew, Luke, John) were likely relatively stable, but other texts such as the Shepherd of Hermas, Revelation, or various Acts of different apostles (such as Thecla) were contested for centuries.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: There were many shrines to Thecla across the Mediterranean, most undoubtedly lost.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Evagrius Scholasticus notes a large basilica to the Proto-Martyr Thecla that emperor Zeno built shortly after 479 CE (Ecclesiastical History 3.8).

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Catacombs apparently dedicated to Thecla are found around the Mediterranean, such as the 4th century catacombs of Thecla outside of Rome or the tomb in Silifke (Aya Tekla), the Convent of St. Thecla in Maaloula (Syria), or the Monastery in Lanarca (Cyprus). Syncletica, an Alexandrian follower of Thecla of the late fourth or early fifth century CE, is reported to have left her family home and resided in a family tomb, where later followers also took up residence (Life and Activity of the Holy and Blessed Syncletica).

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Notes: Cemeteries named in Thecla's honor exist on the Via Ostiense and the Via Aurelia outside of Rome.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: Most notably the Hagia Thecla (Aya Tekla) in Silifke, Syria. Stephen Davis suggests a church built on the site of the Luxor temple in Thebes may have been dedicated to Thecla (Stephen Davis, *The Cult of Saint Thecla*, 174; cf. M. Abdul-Qader Muhammad, 'Preliminary Report on the Excavations Carried Out in the Temple of Luxor, Seasons 1958-1959 and 1959-1960', *Annales du service des antiquités de l'Égypte*, 60 (1968), 252-4, 272, pl. 30).

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: Various artifacts with Thecla's likeness were made such on "clay flasks and oil lamps, engraved on bronze crosses, wooden combs, and stone reliefs, etched onto golden glass medallions" (Stephen Davis, *The Cult of Saint Thecla*, v, cf. 172-4).

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Field doesn't know

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Iconography often features the scene of Thecla being thrown to wild animals, such as on a number of Menas flasks.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Field doesn't know

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Pilgrimages were fairly common to various saints, and Thecla was no exception. Famously, a woman named Egeria wrote a travelogue ("Journey to the Holy Land") in which she recounts a pilgrimage to many holy sites, the shrine of Thecla at Isauria (in modern day Konya) in the late 4th century

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: While not in a strict material/immaterial or Cartesian mind/body dualism, the soul (variously constructed) existed as something distinct from the body, as was common among both Christian and non-Christian philosophers. The debate about the resurrection of the body (vs. only the soul) was present from the days of Paul (cf. 1 Corinthians 15) well into the third century, beyond when The Acts of (Paul and) Thecla was written (cf. Pseudo-Justin, On the Resurrection).

Reference: Stanley Stowers K. A Rereading of Romans: Justice, Jews, and Gentiles. Yale University Press. isbn: 0-300-05357-6.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Christians generally conceived of the "spirit" as a different role than the more concrete body. Inspired by Platonic investigations, Christians variously attributed different features on the different parts of the body (including the soul and/or spirit). Adherents to the cult of Thecla would have shared many of these views, which emphasized control of the bodily passions so as not to make the soul too sick (see Clement of Alexandria, The Instructor).

Reference: John T. Fitzgerald. Passions and Moral Progress in Greco-Roman Thought. Routledge. isbn: 9781134463015.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– No

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: The soul would have been conceived as a type of ether, following the conventional (platonic) physics of the day.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The nature of the afterlife is variously described by different Christian documents, but general living after death is (essentially) accepted by all. In a later ending added to the Acts of (Paul and) Thecla, Thecla does not actually die, but flees attackers into a cave which closes around her. Regardless, Thecla is reported to have visited people long after her (physical) life, such as in the vision of the emperor Zeno (c. 474 CE).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Heaven was generally described as above (cf. the ascension of Jesus to the Father in Acts 1), while the place of punishment ("Hell") was typically described as below (cf. the pit in Revelation 9 & 17). The more philosophically minded might have viewed the afterlife outside of space and time (such as certain Neoplatonic thought, where both "time" and "space" were products of the "One").

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: "Earth" is commonly distinguished from "heaven" (cf. Acts of Thecla 24). Apocalyptic literature often distinguished separate locations for those who were good against those who were bad (cf. Apocalypse of Peter 15, where both afterlives were "outside of this world"). The high god is considered primarily located in Heaven (cf. Acts of Thecla 29, 43).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– Yes

Notes: Most Christians imagined heaven as being above the Earth, as described in Genesis 1, Matthew 3, or John 3:13.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

Notes: Christians largely (though not unanimously) imagined the afterlife of the condemned (the "bad" people) as below (cf. Revelation 9 & 17). Partially, this is a natural extension of the Hebrew concept of Sheol ("grave") which we see in the Hebrew Bible (cf. Genesis 37:35). Transliterated typically as "hades" in the Greek versions of these texts (the Septuagint), the concept of punishment in the afterlife is extended into the Christian concept of Hell, following the spacial conception of "below."

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: It is difficult to determine whether the items found in tombs or on sarcophagi were grave goods specifically relating to Thecla (unless the name "Thecla" is present), and it is unclear that entombing a person in a Thecla-oriented location necessitates any real association of the deceased with the cult. It is unlikely that all buried in the Catacombs of Thecla were pious adherents to the cult of Thecla.

↳ Personal effects:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: Various items have been found with images of Thecla, such as on ampullae in Egypt, though often paired with other figures, such as Saint Menas.

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: Various items have been found in graves that also contained images of Thecla, though it is not likely that those items were deposited specifically because of adherence to the cult of Thecla.

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Catacombs of Thecla were dedicated on the Via Ostiense by Rome, and various depictions of Thecla abound, such as in El Bagawat, the necropolis near Athribis, or the example of an Egyptian grave stele modeling the deceased (named Thecla) after the saint (Coptic Museum no. 8693)

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: The Catacomb of Thecla in Rome on the Via Ostiensis may have been a family tomb of the entombed woman, perhaps containing the bodies of other Theclan enthusiasts.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings range from the high god, angels, to the righteous dead (such as Thecla) who all may interact in the world how they please. On the malevolent side there is the devil (Satan) and demons, who also are seen to plague humanity.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The high god is considered to be the creator God from Genesis, the god of Abraham, who sent his son Jesus (according to Christianity) to die for the salvation of humanity. The high god takes a personal interest in humanity, but especially the saints (like Thecla) who were believed to be righteous, particularly regarding sex (being a virgin).

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: While generally conceived as anthropomorphic (walking, talking, cf. Genesis 3:8, Psalm 10:12, etc), some more philosophically inclined believers influenced by platonic thought began to conceive of the high god as less so.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Yes [specify]: As with Christianity generally, the high god was often seen as being intimately involved with the power structures of the day, particularly since Constantine.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Typically in Late Antiquity the Christian god was seen as trinitarian (variously conceived), with special identity-relations with Jesus, the Holy Spirit, and at times the Church itself (as the "body of Christ")

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Conceived of as the creator god (cf. Genesis 1-2), this god was believed to be omniscient of all things (cf. Matthew 5:6, Psalm 44:21, etc).

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: The high god is believed to be able to see the whole world (cf. Job 28:24).

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: The high god can see both private things and internal/emotional things (cf. Matthew 6).

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: The high god sees all (cf. Matthew 6, Acts of Thecla 24).

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: The high god knows everything about every human being, inside and out (cf. Genesis 6:5). This god can even change people to his will (cf. Exodus 4:21, where this god determines how a ruler will feel).

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Various debated throughout history, the high god's knowledge has typically included future events (cf. Romans 8:28-30, Mark 13:32, etc).

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
– Yes [specify]: Everything there is to know is assumed to be known by the Christian god.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes
Notes: The high god can act directly in events, such as protecting (Acts of Thecla 34), or destroying (Genesis 7-8).

↳ The supreme high god can reward:
– Yes
Notes: The high god rewards those who are righteous (by Christian standards, cf. Matthew 6:3-4, Acts of Thecla 5-6).

↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Yes
Notes: The high god punishes those deemed unrighteous (cf. Matthew 25:31-46, 2 Thessalonians 1:9).

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes
Notes: The high god can act through agents, such as speaking through prophets (Isaiah, Amos, etc) or enabling miraculous abilities (the plagues of Egypt in Exodus through Moses).

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Yes
Notes: The high god expresses pleasure in the world (Genesis 1), in Jesus (Mark 1:11), and also in righteous people (Acts of Thecla 5).

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– Yes
Notes: The high god expresses displeasure at unrighteousness, often preceding punishment (Genesis 6:5-7, Hebrews 4:3). Much has been imagined regarding this god's wrath (Romans 1:18, Revelation 14).

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: Various forms of Christianity go about this differently, though much of this depends on the semantics of "worship" and the trinitarian nature of the Christian deity, which is still debated today.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: The degree to which the Christian god has been described as physical, spiritual, or other, varies widely in antiquity, particularly as neoplatonic ideologies became strongly influential among the intellectuals of the early Catholic Church.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: Generally Christianity believed that God communicated directly with people, particular the prophets (appearing to Moses in the burning bush [Exodus 3], or speaking through a number of prophets [Isaiah, Amos, Hosea, etc]).

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: This has always been subject of debate among Christians, as what it means to "communicate" has been variously defined.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Visions are common, and many Christians saw their god communicating through select texts ("Scripture"), along with the claim of

incarnation (Jesus).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Not all human spirits are assumed to be present, but at least special people are believed to occasionally show up, such as Thecla herself to emperor Zeno (Evagrius, Ecclesiastical History 3.8) or the many recorded miracles of the (deceased) Thecla in The Life and Miracles of Saint Thecla.

Reference: Evagrius (Scholasticus), Evagrius Scholasticus, Évagre le Scolastique. The Ecclesiastical History of Evagrius Scholasticus. Liverpool University Press. isbn: 9780853236054.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Thecla was believed to appear to people after her death, such as to emperor Zeno in the 5th century (Evagrius, Ecclesiastical History 3.8).

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Visions of Thecla have been reported, along with miracles and predicting the future (famously the prediction of emperor Zeno's victory).

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– Yes [specify]: Visions of Saints (Thecla included) know as much as is needed to know for them to do what is described by accounts

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Thecla performing miracles "in-person" after her death is claimed by Pseudo-Basil in the Life and Miracles of Saint Thecla. For example, Miracle 15 describes Thecla appearing on a ship during a storm and "she grasped the rigging, pulled the cables, hoisted the canvas and rebuked the storm," then Thecla "set the ship upright, and anchored it."

Reference: Linda Honey Ann. Thekla: Text and Context with a First English Translation of the Miracles (PhD dissertation). University of Calgary.

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: Thecla was believed to communicate to people after her death, such as to emperor Zeno in the 5th century (Evagrius, Ecclesiastical History 3.8).

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Angels are commonly believed to exist in Christianity, and this applies to the cult of Thecla as well (Acts of Thecla 5).

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: Angels, God (and other trinitarian identities), and saints are essentially omniscient as required by the narrative being told.
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Angels and demons are often considered affecting the world, either in the past (Genesis 6) or the future (Revelation).
- ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Angels are thought to influence human actions in history (Genesis 16, 19, Matthew 1-2, etc).
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Notes: While the Christian supernatural beings are not based on a family in the sense of traditional Greek mythology, various attributions of familial identity are applied, particularly with Jesus as the son of God, or at times angels being the sons of God.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: While the highest deity is all-powerful, the Trinity (as it developed) was essentially a unity (of sorts), while angels occupied a subordinate role (typically messengers), and saints like Thecla were in Heaven, but active on Earth in visions, apparitions, or other visitations in order to help or guide people.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: The high god is conceived of as watching all behavior and thoughts, and the cult of Thecla likely prioritized physical/sexual purity more than others (Acts of Thecla 5-6).

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– No

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Christianity generally has always cared about sexual practice, but the Cult of Thecla would have prioritized virginity (particularly for women) most.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The Cult of Thecla would have cared variously about what they perceived to be divine ordinances as interpreted from various Christian and Jewish texts.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Punishment is generally believed to occur in the afterlife, but various punishments may occur in this world (as is expressed many places in the New Testament and the Christian Bible as a whole).

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: The cause of punishment for Christians was generally viewed as either 1) not being a Christian or 2) being a bad Christian. When non-Christians die, they would be sent to Hell where various Christians have hypothesized differing punishments such as fire, total destruction (cf. Matthew 10:28), or torments customized to individual sins (such as in the Apocalypse of Peter).

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: While the high god makes the judgment call on whether someone is punished, this high god is not seen as being delivered by this same high god. Punishments may be delivered before death, however, but sometimes meted out by angels or demons.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Any positive or negative event in this life can be attributed to the divine plan, either as reward or punishment for actions.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: Various rewards are bestowed on righteous people by God, Jesus, angels, or even Thecla. For example, as recorded in Miracle 41 of the 5th century *Life and Miracles of Saint Thecla* (Pseudo-Basil), the narrator was healed of an ear infection by the (deceased) Thecla, "since [Thecla] knows how to return very generous <recompense>."

Reference: Linda Honey Ann. *Thekla: Text and Context with a First English Translation of the Miracles* (PhD diss). University of Calgary.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The extent to which dead saints give rewards varied, but they were generally seen as able to affect one's life.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– No

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
– No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
– No
- ↳ Other [specify]
– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus is believed to be the messiah in Christianity, as attested in most New Testament texts.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Notes: God the father is believed to know when the messiah will return, but humans are not (Mark 13:32, Matthew 24:36).

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: Christians have widely debated the means and methods of accomplishing this, Jesus is generally seen as allowing the salvation of humanity.

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

Notes: While the Jewish concept of the Messiah was often conceived of as a political warrior-king type (such as Simon bar Kokhba in the second century), Jesus was not generally considered a political figure, as he was crucified by the imperial authorities.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– No

Notes: While the book of Hebrews seems to apply a priestly role to Jesus, he wasn't generally considered restoring anything, but rather ushering in a new age of salvation for humanity.

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: The Christian messiah (Jesus) was also seen as an embodiment (of some kind) of the high god, and would return in judgment upon the whole world, generally seen as destroying all non-believers and establishing a new kingdom of god.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

Notes: Many Christians at all times have believed their generation would see the eschaton.

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– Yes

Notes: Specified by the high god, but not known to adherents.

- ↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:
 - No
- ↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:
 - No
- ↳ Eschaton at some other time:
 - No
- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:
 - No
- ↳ Divine judgment event:
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of a new political system:
 - Yes
- ↳ Establishment of a new religious system:
 - No
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:
 - Yes
 - ↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:
 - No
 - ↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: While all "Christians" would survive, there is a tradition that some Christians would be "false," so only the "true" Christians would survive (cf. Matthew 7:21).

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Other survival condition:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: While generally following basic Christian ideologies of morality, the cult of Thecla prized virginity, chastity, and reverence to the saint(s). The Acts of (Paul and) Thecla prizes virginity above all else (cf. chapters 5 and 6 especially).

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Christianity was approached differently in antiquity depending on whether the powers that be were advocating a Christian moral agenda. Before Constantine (4th century), Christians would have juxtaposed their "higher" morality against that of "the world" (cf. John 15:19, Romans 12:2, 1 Corinthians 1). Thecla herself was supposedly rejecting the conventions of her town (getting married) in order to follow Paul's preaching about virginity (Acts of [Paul and] Thecla 10).

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society (excepting slaves, aliens)

– All individuals within society

– All individuals (any time period)

Notes: While the general Christian moral norms would have applied (whatever those may have been at the time), adherents to the cult of Thecla elevated women's roles in the moral community, emphasizing virginity and martyrdom (the former being more expected than the latter).

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: While highly prized, and many people used Thecla as an example of pure Christian virginity/chastity, it was not a requirement.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: While complete sexual abstinence was not required, it was highly respected.

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: As with most forms of Christianity, various sexual acts were prohibited (such as homosexual acts, bestiality, incest, and other forms of sex that violated ancient cultural norms).

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: While women's sexuality was generally less nuanced in antiquity, a woman would have been expected either to remain a virgin or to marry and have children (with a man).

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Various items, either monetary donations or other, were offered at shrines. This would not have been technically required, but is more of a de facto reality of cult participants, depending on ability.

↳ To other in-group members:

– No

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: While particular small-scale rituals were not enforced, they are likely to have occurred in most households, particularly of those holding a special veneration to one particular saint or another.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Notes: While large-scale rituals would not have been required, our ability to gauge who was and was not a participant in the cult of Thecla is largely gauged on our observances of rituals, particularly pilgrimages.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The cult was one of voluntary participation, with varying levels of adherence throughout the Mediterranean. Some locations, such as Seleucia, were far more observant than others.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: While not necessarily institutional or universal, shrines of Thecla would provide shelter, especially to those making a pilgrimage to it, which includes providing food to weary travelers.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Various charities, which may or may not be cult-specific (or even Christian) were common enough in antiquity. See Peter Brown, *Power and Persuasion in Late Antiquity*.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: While giving to the poor, either in forms of shelter or food, there was not a strict institutionalized effort to relieve poverty; poverty was a state assumed. The Acts of Thecla does record Thecla herself as giving her inheritance to the poor (chapter 41).

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Various charities, which may or may not be cult-specific (or even Christian) were common enough in antiquity. See Peter Brown, *Power and Persuasion in Late Antiquity*.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: Various charitable acts were part of most cult systems. See Peter Brown, *Power and Persuasion in Late Antiquity*.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Various charities, which may or may not be cult-specific (or even Christian) were common enough in antiquity. See Peter Brown, *Power and Persuasion in Late Antiquity*.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: While women could certainly be educated, the same opportunities were not available to them (particularly politically or through the Church).

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: While the official nature of Thecla shrines vary by location, adherents would be expected to respect local authorities (under Roman law), or even specific temple authorities, such as in Mareotis (if not within the temple to Menas itself; see Stephen J. Davis, *The Cult of Saint Thecla*, 126-133).

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: A variety of donors can contribute food to a cult with varying levels of involvement with the cult itself.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The ancient Roman Empire is famous for instituting water systems across its empire.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Roman Empire established many roads throughout the the Mediterranean.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: While not required, offerings were somewhat de facto what tied someone to the cult, if one could afford it.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents in the Mediterranean would largely have been subject to Roman law, which included taxes.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: Temple guards were common, though they weren't a "police force" as such.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: General protection by the local forces would have been common, whether attached to the cult of Thecla specifically or not (geographically varied).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents in the Mediterranean would largely have been subject to Roman law.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents in the Mediterranean would largely have been subject to Roman law.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: Exile was common, especially during the times of Christological controversies. These were often in Egypt, particularly the Kharga and Dakhla Oases. "Rogue" Christians being sent into exile fueled the rise of Christian settlements in Egypt, particularly those which may not have been strictly adherent to Catholic Orthodoxy.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents in the Mediterranean would largely have been subject to Roman law.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: While not as popular among the military as the cult of Mithras (in the early centuries), soldiers would not have been banned from adherence to the cult of Thecla, however rare.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Generally speaking the imperial Roman army, along with local military factions, were responsible for the security of temples and shrines, even if only as general peacekeepers.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Greek, Coptic, and Syriac would have been primary languages of these early communities, subject to local customs. For those who could afford tutors, literacy would have been part of a regular pedagogical course. Otherwise, illiteracy is the working assumption for the vast majority of adherents.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The foundational text of the cult, the Acts of (Paul and) Thecla, was written in Greek. The entire New Testament, including the letters of Paul and Acts of the Apostles on which the Acts of (Paul and) Thecla was based, were also written in Greek. The more educated of cult leaders would have known and utilized these texts in constructing the narratives of Thecla.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Christians would have followed the general Christian calendar as it existed at the time (essentially the Roman calendar), with Thecla's feast day recognized as September 23 in the East by the time of Bede's Martyrology (8th century).

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: Most food would have been provided through donations and benefactions.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: Rich benefactors donated to the sustenance of the cult; the degree to which these benefactors were adherents to the cult itself or desiring status bolstering through such benefactions remains an open question.

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